

PILOT TESTS

In Real Port Environments

May 2025

Trondheim

📍 Trondheim, Norway

Bonus coverage: A closer look at the December test at Drammen Port

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From Research to Innovative Results

To ensure close collaboration between the project end users (security agencies and port authorities) and the technical partners throughout the project lifecycle, SMAUG will showcase and validate the multiple solutions developed during the project in 3 pilots. These will be executed, and their outcomes will be evaluated in a real port environment, specifically at the ports of Valencia (Spain), Elefsina (Greece), Heraklion (Greece), and Drammen (Norway).

- Pilot Summary

Trondheim, Norway

Our partners from Maritime Robotics & Elistair are sharing the collective insights and updates on the Aerial Detection tests conducted so far in the Trondheim area, with the **Elistair Chronos dronebox** integrated on Maritime Robotics Mariner USV.

Aerial Detection in Trondheim

The objective of this test was to obtain proof of concept for the integration of the tethered drone with MAROB's Unmanned Surface Vehicle (USV). Several technical aspects were addressed, including mechanical integration, power transfer from the USV to the drone, communication between the systems, and drone behaviour during take-off, landing, and flight operations.

Prior to take-off, a series of software updates was implemented to ensure reliable operation in maritime conditions. The network architecture was then configured using the **Zerotier solution**, enabling wireless access with wide coverage and minimal latency in system response.

However, issues related to video stream quality were identified. As this solution will not be fully operational in time for the final demonstration, an alternative communication system will need to be implemented.

On day one, the weather conditions were:

- Static electricity: 0J/kg
- Temperature: 8°C
- Wind and gusts: 30 km/h and 60km/h
- Light rain

Testing of both the USV and the tethered UAV was conducted in port under challenging wind conditions. The drone experienced difficulty maintaining position above the USV and was significantly affected by wind gusts. Gusts of 60 km/h correspond to the operational limit of Elistair's drone, which constrained performance during this session.

On day two, the weather conditions were:

- Static electricity: 0J/kg
- Temperature: 5°C
- Wind and gusts: 22 km/h and 45km/h
- No rain

Under improved weather conditions, multiple successful flights were completed. The drone demonstrated stable and reliable performance, covering a substantial area of the bay. A total of ten deployments were carried out in both static and follow-me modes, at vessel speeds of up to 7 knots. U-turn manoeuvres were also performed, with the drone maintaining excellent positional stability.

During the final flight, controlled wave conditions were generated to assess take-off and landing performance. The drone operated flawlessly under these circumstances. As wave heights remained below 60 cm, further testing in more representative sea states will be required to validate performance under harsher maritime conditions.

Bonus coverage

December test at Drammen Port

The trials were conducted using MAROB's "Otter" USV, equipped with an advanced Autonomous Navigation System enabling precise waypoint tracking and adaptive route management in dynamic maritime environments. The platform features seamless integration with the Kongsberg EM2042 multibeam sonar, ensuring high-resolution bathymetric data acquisition. In addition, the USV is fitted with AIS and complementary situational awareness sensors, enabling real-time vessel tracking and enhanced operational safety.

The onboard system supports real-time logging and processing of data from a broad range of sensors, including multibeam sonar systems,

LiDAR, and 360-degree cameras, thereby providing a comprehensive above- and below-water operational picture.

For underwater detection and seabed assessment, the Kongsberg EM2042 was deployed as the primary sensing system. The main objective was to map the designated area in preparation for the 2026 demonstrator. Acquired data will undergo detailed post-processing to enhance overall quality and generate a high-accuracy base map. Following this process, the dataset may allow identification of features of interest that could serve as representative detection examples, supporting training and scenario preparation for 2026. The resulting bathymetric map will be delivered in GeoTIFF format.

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